

Print: 3082-4060
Online: 3082-4079

PACIFICUS

A LITERARY MAGAZINE

VOLUME 1

ISSUE 3 | JULY - SEPTEMBER ISSUE
A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

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A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue III | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

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“GUIDING, INSPIRING, AND LEADING: MY REFLECTION ON ED205”

The Course School Organization, Administration and Supervision or ED205 has been a big help in my teaching career as an educator ever since i was employ in Department of Education (Ministry of Basic, Higher, Technical Education of Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao or MBHTE-BARMM). The course’s objective, the principles of school organization, helps me to make an organizational structure and process the educational institution and to facilitate teaching and learning effectively. It also focuses on supervisory and leadership where in fact serves as a crucial aspect in managing students' learning. Supervision focuses on the day-to-day management of tasks, ensuring that the work is completely finished thoroughly, efficiently and effectively. While Leadership, furthermore, involves inspiring and influencing others to share a vision, it also fosters growth, and helps the teacher to create a positive atmosphere.

When I was in my high school year, I never imagined myself to be in a teaching field/career. When I graduated from high school, I started living my life the way I wanted. Since I am a member of LGBT, it is hard for me to get a decent job, so I started to roam around and do whatever I want. Then one day, I realized I should not let myself end like this. So I decided to enroll in one of the colleges here in Cotabato City. And I ended up enrolling and getting Education as my course since it is the closest college at the said school (hilarious). And with the help of my mother and my older sister who happens to be in a government position I managed to get back on my feet and started to get back in studying and after four productive years I managed to finish my studies and graduated on the same course. Then I try to take the Board Examination for Teachers and I passed way back in 2014.

Taking up this course made me learn that effective supervisory and leadership strategies should require a depth of skills and practices. These include strong communication between employees, time management, representatives and close supervisions. It also helps me to grow as an educator by means of guiding, motivating and mentoring my colleagues here at our school. My point of view is to enhance my abilities in teaching, influence others and to inspire my colleagues and very importantly our learners.

These are the challenges I encountered:

- Internet connection/power interruption (because of road concreting)
- Weather
- Time

I manage to make a way to join every zoom meeting and reporting by transferring my location to school for better internet connectivity and power supply. This course may give me a lot of hardships but together with my classmates I can say that we manage to pull this off. This course serves as a foundation for my MAEd journey. I have learned many ideas to become a better educator in spite of many challenges in our education system here in the Philippines. The trials and tribulations that I had encountered during these past few weeks because of hectic schedules has also given me the courage and strength that will serve the education system much better.

In conclusion, this course School Organization, Administration and Supervision (ED205) taught me a lot to build up my academic career as an LGBT Educator and as a student. Being a teacher means learning is never-ending. As I wrapped up this Reflective Essay of mine I would like to give my overwhelming gratitude to our Professor **Oliver Ortiz** for making this summer class very informative, and first time only in a Masteral friendly environment. Thank you very much.

